

Safe Nonlinear Model Predictive Control using a Learned Approximate Control-Invariant Set

Gianni Lunardi¹, Asia La Rocca¹, Matteo Saveriano¹ and Andrea Del Prete¹

Abstract—In recent years, both model-based and data-driven control methods have advanced the capabilities of robotic systems, enabling more agile and dynamic movements. However, ensuring safety within these frameworks remains a significant challenge. This extended abstract presents a novel Model Predictive Control (MPC) approach that ensures safety through a conservative approximation of a safe set (a.k.a. control-invariant set). This method replaces the classic terminal constraint with a novel receding constraint, which leads to a higher number of completed tasks, while retaining safety guarantees. The approach was tested on a simulated robotic manipulator, showing clear advantages over existing state-of-the-art MPC methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

Maintain safety is critical in most of robotics applications, due to the recently growing complexity of robotic platforms and control methods. Reinforcement Learning and other recent data-driven algorithms build black-box policies, whose safety is hard to certify. One of the main tools to ensure safety in dynamical systems is the so-called control-invariant set (a.k.a. *safe set*) [1], [2]. The knowledge of such a set, enables recursive constraint satisfaction, known as *recursive feasibility*, for model-based control methods. Nevertheless, safe sets are almost impossible to compute, in an exact way, for nonlinear systems in general. There exist algorithms to compute approximated safe sets [3]–[6], but then safety cannot be guaranteed anymore since the control-invariant set is not exact.

In this work, we introduce a novel MPC scheme that provide safety under weaker assumptions with respect to state-of-the-art control invariant theory.

II. METHOD

Let us consider a discrete-time dynamical system $x_{i+1} = f(x_i, u_i)$, with state x and control u respectively bounded in the sets \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{U} . We can define the *M-step Backward Reachable Set* \mathcal{V} as:

$$\mathcal{V} \triangleq \{x_0 \in \mathcal{X} \mid \exists \{u_i\}_0^{M-1} : x_M = x_{M-1}, x_i \in \mathcal{X}, u_i \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i = 0, \dots, M-1\}, \quad (1)$$

thus the subset of \mathcal{X} starting from which it is possible to reach an equilibrium state in M time steps. Since a steady-state condition is always reachable, the set \mathcal{V} is control-invariant.

¹The authors are with the Industrial Engineering Department, University of Trento, Via Sommarive 11, 38123, Trento, Italy. {name.surname}@unitn.it

Funded by the European Union under NextGenerationEU, PRIN 2022 project STARLIT Prot. n. 2022ZE9J9J (CUP n. E53D23001130006), PRIN project ARIEL (CUP n. E53D23001020001), and project INVERSE under Grant Agreement n. 101136067.

Fig. 1. Case of Receding-Constraint MPC with short horizon. In the MPC loop 4, the receding constraint moves ahead due to constraint satisfaction in the previous step.

A general MPC problem can be defined as follows:

$$\underset{\{x_i\}_0^N, \{u_i\}_0^{N-1}}{\text{minimize}} \quad \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \ell_i(x_i, u_i) + \ell_N(x_N) \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad x_0 = x_{init} \quad (2b)$$

$$x_{i+1} = f(x_i, u_i) \quad i = 0 \dots N-1 \quad (2c)$$

$$x_i \in \mathcal{X}, u_i \in \mathcal{U} \quad i = 0 \dots N-1 \quad (2d)$$

$$x_N \in \mathcal{X}_N, \quad (2e)$$

where $\ell(\cdot)/\ell_N(\cdot)$ is the running/terminal cost, x_{init} is the current state, and $\mathcal{X}_N \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ is the terminal set [7]. Recursive Feasibility (RF) can be exploited to guarantee constraint satisfaction, thus safety, in MPC. This condition is achieved by imposing a *control-invariant* set as terminal constraint for the state x , such that the MPC problem will be feasible forever. For most nonlinear systems, only approximations $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ of the real set \mathcal{V} can be computed. Since $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ is typically not control-invariant, RF of the MPC is lost. Nonetheless, some algorithms, such as [6], can be exploited to made $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ conservative by an opportune pick of a safety margin, to have $\hat{\mathcal{V}} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$.

We introduce an innovative MPC framework, made by a receding-constraint MPC formulation and a safe task-abortion strategy. Given an $r \in [1, N]$, we had noticed that if the state $x_r \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}$, then $x_1 \in \mathcal{V}$ since from x_1 we can reach x_r . Based on this observation, the time step for which we constraint the state

in the approximated *safe set* can be adapted online. Denoting $x_{r|k}$ as the state at time step $k+r$ predicted in the MPC problem at time step k , $x_{r|k-1} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}$ implies $x_{r-1|k} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}$ under the assumption of bounded disturbances and no modeling errors. This procedure establish safety for at least r loops, in which the *receding constraint* slides toward the head of the horizon. To extend RF for more than r MPC steps, we propose to keep (2e) as soft terminal constraint, with $\mathcal{X}_N = \hat{\mathcal{V}}$. Then, if for any $i > r$ the condition $x_i \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}$ is satisfied, we can impose $r = i - 1$ at the following MPC cycle. Otherwise, we let r decrease. An example is depicted in Fig. 1.

If we reach $r = 1 + L$ (with L being a non-negative hyper-parameter as small as possible) then we trigger the safe task abort procedure. Suppose that we have access to two computational units, A and B, and the following OCP can be solved within $L + 1$ time steps ($L \in [0, N - 1]$) for any $x_{init} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\{x_i\}_0^M, \{u_i\}_0^{M-1}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} \ell_i(x_i, u_i) + \ell_M(x_M) \\ & \text{subject to} && (2b), (2c), (2d), x_M = x_{M-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where the cost function is an L2 penalization of the velocity, to support the convergence to an equilibrium position. Suppose we trigger the safe abort procedure at MPC loop k . We can follow these steps:

- 1) unit A apply the MPC solution computed at iteration $k - 1$ to reach the terminal state $x_{L+1|k-1} \in \hat{\mathcal{V}}$;
- 2) simultaneously, unit B solves OCP (3), using $x_{L+1|k-1}$ as initial state;
- 3) once $x_{L+1|k-1}$ is reached, the solution of OCP (3) is followed to safely attain an equilibrium state.

OCP (3) is always feasible assuming $\hat{\mathcal{V}} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

To evaluate the role of the *safe abort* and the *receding constraint*, we compared our novel MPC scheme with a *Naive* approach, thus problem (2) with $\mathcal{X}_N = \mathcal{X}$, and a scheme (*STWA*) that introduces a soft terminal constraint set $\mathcal{X}_N = \hat{\mathcal{V}}$, with *safe abort* triggered whenever $x_{N|k} \notin \hat{\mathcal{V}}$.

For the simulations, we have used a 3-joint manipulator. The task is to regulate the state to $x^{\text{ref}} = (q^{\text{max}} - 0.05, \bar{q}, \bar{q}, 0, 0, 0)$, with $\bar{q} = (q^{\text{max}} + q^{\text{min}})/2$. The running cost penalizes deviations from x^{ref} and control efforts:

$$\begin{aligned} l(x, u) &= \|x - x^{\text{ref}}\|_Q^2 + \|u\|_R^2 \\ Q &= \text{diag}([500, 10^{-4}I_5]), \quad R = 10^{-4}I_3, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where I_h is the identity matrix with size h . We can check if the state x belongs to $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ with the following inequality:

$$(1 - \alpha)\phi(x) - \|\dot{q}\| \geq 0. \quad (5)$$

The function $\phi(\cdot)$ is Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) that, given the joint position and the velocity direction as inputs, provides the maximum joint velocity norm [6]. The parameter $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is introduced as safety margin, to certify $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ as subset of \mathcal{V} .

TABLE I
PERFORMANCES OF THE DIFFERENT MPC APPROACHES (INCLUDING OUR NOVEL SCHEME) AMONG A TOTAL OF 100 TESTS.

MPC	Completed	Aborted	Failed
Naive	69	-	31
STWA	70	22	8
Receding	77	20	3

We have considered 100 random initial joint positions q_0 , shared between the different MPC formulations. The simulations have been run with time step $dt = 5$ ms, horizon $N = 35$ and $\alpha = 10\%$. The outcomes of the tests, divided into completed, safely aborted or failed tasks, are reported in Table I. *STWA* completed practically the same number of tasks as *Naive*, but in some cases were able to successfully abort the task, reducing the number of failed tasks. In general, *Receding* performed the best, since it completed more tasks and safely aborted most of the remaining tests, failing only 3 times.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have introduced a novel Receding-Constraint MPC formulation that ensures recursive feasibility under a less restrictive assumption regarding the safe set compared to traditional methods. Additionally, we proposed a task-abortion strategy that enables the system to reach an equilibrium state when the potential for constraint violation is identified. While our method relies on weaker assumption than standard approaches, these assumptions are still hard to verify, which can lead to constraint violation, as shown in our tests. Future research will focus on reducing the computation times ($L + 1$ time steps) of the safe-abort OCP (3) using warm-start techniques [8]. We also plan to include Cartesian constraints to avoid collision with static obstacles.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Blanchini, "Set invariance in control," *Automatica*, vol. 35, pp. 1747–1767, 1999.
- [2] L. Grüne and J. Pannek, *Nonlinear model predictive control*. Springer, 2017.
- [3] P.-A. Coquelin, S. Martin, and R. Munos, "A dynamic programming approach to viability problems," in *IEEE International Symposium on Approximate Dynamic Programming and Reinforcement Learning*, 2007, pp. 178–184.
- [4] K. C. Hsu, V. Rubies-Royo, C. J. Tomlin, and J. F. Fisac, "Safety and Liveness Guarantees through Reach-Avoid Reinforcement Learning," *Robotics: Science and Systems*, 2021.
- [5] C. Dawson, S. Gao, and C. Fan, "Safe Control With Learned Certificates : A Survey of Neural Lyapunov , Barrier , and Contraction Methods for Robotics and Control," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 1749–1767, 2023.
- [6] A. La Rocca, M. Saveriano, and A. Del Prete, "VBOC: Learning the Viability Boundary of a Robot Manipulator using Optimal Control," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 2023.
- [7] D. Q. Mayne, J. B. Rawlings, C. V. Rao, and P. O. Scokaert, "Constrained model predictive control: Stability and optimality," *Automatica*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 789–814, 2000.
- [8] N. Mansard, A. Del Prete, M. Geisert, S. Tonneau, and O. Stasse, "Using a Memory of Motion to Efficiently Warm-Start a Nonlinear Predictive Controller," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2018, pp. 2986–2993.